

Report on eco-tourism development needs and opportunities at Vlora & Feasibility Concept of the Nature-based Ecotourism at Karaburun Sazan MPA

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Introduction

The Karaburun Peninsula is a strip of land that goes from Orikum to the sea. It hosts cliffs, caves and beaches of rare beauty. The Karaburun promontory has peaks that exceed 1000 m in height, it is very green and has cliffs overlooking the sea, as well as being scattered with bays. The island of Sazan (Fig. 1.1) has been open to tour boats since 2015. It is an island characterised by crystal clear waters and beautiful beaches.

Albania's Karaburun-Sazan Marine Protected Area (hereafter, K-S MPA) was established in 2010 as a National Marine Park. The MPA, with a total surface of 12,750 ha, stretches 1 nm along the Western and Eastern coast of the Karaburun Peninsula and 1 nm around Sazan Island, excluding the military port.

MPAs represent core attractions for sustainable tourism. K-S MPA being characterised with pristine landscapes, high-quality habitats and biodiversity, both on land and in the sea, history and cultural heritage, could be seen as a vehicle for sustainable tourism. That could generate positive economic impacts and benefits to the local population, and provide a strong potential for conservation actions.

Fig. 1.1 Sazan Island (Photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Marine ecosystem good and services

Social, economic and environmental impacts of development, both short and long term, need to be identified and measured to ensure that environmental decision making is sustainable (Costanza et al. 1997, Rieb et al. 2017).

The Ecosystem Approach is a holist approach that aims to integrate the management of land, water and living resources to promote conservation and sustainability (Small et al. 2017). This approach is increasingly adopted in environmental policy (e.g. Marine Strategy Framework Directive). It requires the integration of social, economic and environmental demands and pressures. The concept of ecosystem goods and services, which are ‘the direct and indirect benefits people obtain from ecosystems (Beaumont et al. 2007, Beaumont et al. 2008), are fundamental to boost the integration. Evaluating ecological processes and resources as the goods and services they provide help to simplify the complexity of the environment into a series of functions, which can be more easily understood by policymakers and non-scientists.

Natural ecosystems exert functions without which our lives would become far more complex and challenging. These functions are ecosystem services (Barbier 2017) and can be defined as all the activities that an ecosystem performs naturally (“Ecosystem services are the suite of benefits that ecosystem provide to the humanity”, Cardinale et al. 2002). For example, coastal waters supply us with food and other resources while at the same time absorbing many of our waste products like urban discharges.

According to the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA, Millennium Ecosystem Assessment 2003), the services (Fig.1.2) that the marine ecosystem provides for marine and coastal areas can be divided into three main categories:

- Production services are the products obtained from the ecosystem
- Regulating services are the benefits obtained from the regulation of ecosystem processes
- Cultural services are the nonmaterial benefits people obtain from ecosystems
- Supporting services are those that are necessary for the production of all other ecosystem services, but do not yield direct benefits to humans

The provisioning services include the provision of food, biotic materials and biofuels, and water storage and provision. The regulating and maintenance services are those that lessen the environmental change, e.g. water purification, air quality regulation, coastal protection, climate regulation, and life cycle maintenance and biological regulation. The cultural services represent human value and enjoyment, i.e. symbolic and aesthetic values, recreation and tourism, and cognitive effects (Hein et al. 2006).

Fig. 1.2 Coastal ecosystem services (source: <https://nca2014.globalchange.gov/report/regions/coasts>)

Posidonia oceanica meadows’, for example, give protection against the erosive action of the waves on the coasts. They serve as nurseries for the growth of fish and provide food and shelter to a wide variety of marine species. Following the MEA definition of ecosystem service and according to Binet et al. 2016, the ecosystem services identified within the K-S MPA and their main actors are the following:

- Provisioning services: artisanal fisheries
- Cultural services: boat excursions, (visible wildlife, aesthetic scenery, accessible beaches), dive centres, tourism fishing (on board tourism operated by fishers)
- Regulating services: seawater quality, carbon storage and climate mitigation, protection against natural hazards
- Supporting services: biodiversity, spawning grounds and nursery

In 2016, the estimate economic value of the K-S MPA ecosystem services was equal to 1’684 billion per year. Regulatory services represent the most important part of these services (95% of the total value) while provisional services and cultural services represent 2.5% of the total value respectively (Binet et al. 2016).

Coastal tourism is a growing industrial sector in the Mediterranean basin. This and other human activities, which take place along the coast, share space and resources, leading to disagreements for different uses. Furthermore, the excessive exploitation of natural resources degrades and exhausts coastal habitats, with negative feedback

effects for all human activities. Therefore, both tourism and other human activities need to consider their dependence on coastal ecosystem services and act at a technical and political level to reach a compromise that preserves long-term natural resources (Drius et al. 2019).

The growing demand for ecosystem services is complicated by the decrease in the ability of ecosystems to provide these services. A country can increase its food supply by decreasing the size of its catch or by converting forest into agriculture, for example, but in doing so, it decreases the offer of services that may be of equal or greater importance, such as clean water or ecotourism destinations (Beaumont et al. 2007, Beaumont et al. 2008). The excessive demand for ecosystem services deriving from economic growth, demographic changes and individual choices are some of the causes of the degradation of ecosystem services. Market mechanisms do not always ensure the conservation of ecosystem services because there are no markets for services such as cultural services, or because policies and institutions do not allow people living within the ecosystem to benefit from the services.

If properly managed, the creation of ecotourism opportunities in a country can create strong economic incentives for the maintenance of cultural services provided by ecosystems. Still, if poorly managed, ecotourism activities can degrade the resource on which they depend.

Mediterranean Sea coralligenous habitats: threats and conservation

The Mediterranean Sea is an oligotrophic temperate sea that harbours almost 10% of world's marine species, and it is considered a marine biodiversity hotspot (Bianchi & Morri 2000, Boudouresque 2004, Ballesteros 2006, Coll et al. 2010). Coralligenous reefs, mesophotic biogenic structures (*sensu* Ballesteros 2006) are among the most important marine benthic subtidal habitats in the Mediterranean Sea because of their high species diversity, structural and functional complexity (see Ballesteros 2006, Ingrosso et al. 2018 and references therein). K-S MPA is characterised by coralligenous outcrops (Kashta et al. 2010, Andromede Oceanology 2016, Shkurti 2019).

Benthic assemblages of the coralligenous reefs (Fig. 1.3) have two levels of complexity: a layer coating the substratum made by Encrusting Calcareous Rhodophytes, bryozoans, scleractinian corals, serpulid polychaetes and vermetid gastropods, and an upper layer formed by species protruding from the substrate, like gorgonians and sponges (Ballesteros 2006, Ingrosso et al. 2018). Coralligenous assemblages are dominated by long-lived, slow-growing and low-recruitment species with overall low population dynamics (Ballesteros 2006, Calvo et al. 2011, Teixido et al. 2011).

Fig. 1.3 Coralligenous habitat in the Mediterranean Sea (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Coralligenous habitats provide ecosystem services (e.g. food provision and nutrient cycling; Micheli et al. 2013). Among them, coralligenous habitats play an essential role in the carbon cycle, thanks to the carbon sequestration by calcareous organisms.

However, coralligenous assemblages (Fig. 1.4) are highly threatened by anthropogenic disturbances (Claudet & Fraschetti 2010, Coll et al. 2010, Coll et al. 2012, Bevilacqua et al. 2018) such as nutrient enrichment (e.g. Gennaro & Piazzì 2011, Piazzì et al. 2018), increases in water turbidity and sedimentation rates (e.g. Balata et al. 2005, Mateos-Molina et al. 2015), invasion from non-indigenous species (e.g. Piazzì & Balata 2008, de Caralt & Cebrian 2013), mechanical damages by anchoring, fishing nets and divers frequentation (e.g. Bavestrello et al. 1997, Hinz 2017), and by global climate change-related disturbances like exceptional storms (Teixido et al. 2013), acidification and thermal anomalies (Martin & Gattuso 2009, Zunino et al. 2017). Thermal anomalies, which may induce physiological stress and increase the susceptibility to pathogens, coupled with the reduced food availability linked to the stratification of the water column in summers, seem to lie at the basis of sessile benthic communities mass mortality events (mainly sponges, cnidarians, bivalves, ascidians and bryozoans) recorded in recent decades in the north-western Mediterranean Sea (e.g. Cerrano et al. 2000, Garrabou et al. 2009, Calvo et al. 2011, Crisci et al. 2011, Turicchia et al. 2018).

The rising concern about the increase of anthropogenic pressures and their consequences on the European coasts (Airoldi & Beck 2007) has induced the European Union to propose and develop new conservation and recovering strategies. Since 2000, three are the directives embraced by the European Union concerning the coastal marine environments: the Water Framework Directive (WFD), the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), and the Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD), which are oriented to assess the water quality, the good environmental status and the sustainable use plans, respectively. In 2008 the Barcelona Convention's Action plan was adopted for the conservation of coralligenous outcrops and other calcareous bioconcretions in the Mediterranean Sea. Although not legally binding, it asserts that 'coralligenous/maërl assemblages should be granted legal protection at the same level as *Posidonia oceanica* meadows' (UNEP-MAP-RAC/SPA 2008, updated in 2016).

Fig. 1.4 Coralligenous assemblages in the Mediterranean Sea (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Sustainable tourism

According to the UNWTO, the sustainable tourism is: “Tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities” (UNWTO 2005).

There is a broad consensus that tourism development should be sustainable; however, the problem is of how to manage tourism growth to achieve this object. Tourism is one of the world's largest and fastest-growing industries, and when not well managed will place high stress on the environment and local cultures. Sustainable tourism is sensitive to these dangers and seeks to protect the pristine tourist destinations and the local culture. There are several ways to reduce the impact of tourism and approach the problem more sustainably:

- Respecting and supporting the integrity of local cultures by favouring businesses which conserve cultural heritage and traditional values
- Conserving resources by seeking out environmentally conscious businesses

The relationship between tourism and sustainable development is based on three main pillars (UNWTO 2005):

- The interaction among tourists, the local communities and the environment;
- The increasing awareness of the visitors about environmental issues and different cultures;
- The dependency of the tourist sector on being in a place of intact and clean environments, attractive natural areas, authentic historical and cultural traditions, and welcoming hosts.

Tourism can be a positive force for sustainable development by providing direct income and opportunities for activities development and employment creation. However, if political and management actions do not sustain tourism, by increasing the pressure on the environment, it could be a cause of environmental degradation.

Nowadays, responsible tourism is seen as a pathway to sustainable tourism. Responsible tourism and sustainable tourism have the same goal: sustainable development. The pillars of responsible tourism are therefore the same as those of sustainable tourism – environmental integrity, social justice and economic development. The emphasis on responsibility means that everyone involved in tourism (government, operators, transport operators, NGOs, tourists, local communities, industry associations) is responsible for achieving the goals set. Stakeholders, both individuals and organisations, play a crucial role in pursuing sustainable tourism (Aas et al. 2005).

The Global Sustainable Tourism Council (GSTC) is the international body for promoting sustainable tourism practices, fostering the adoption of universal sustainable tourism principles and building demand for sustainable travel.

The governments are essential players in defining sustainable tourism as well. Indeed, they set the national strategy of sustainable tourism; they need to take into account the carrying capacity of the area of interest. This

is the capacity of visitors in an area that can sustainably tolerate without damaging the environment or culture of the surrounding area. The carrying capacity can be altered and revised in time and with changing perceptions and values.

Non-governmental organisations are one of the stakeholders in advancing sustainable tourism. Their roles can range from spearheading sustainable tourism practices to doing research.

Local communities benefit from sustainable tourism through income increasing, job creation, and infrastructure development. Tourism revenues bring economic growth to nature-based tourist destinations, which can raise the standard of living in destination communities. Moreover, the increase in tourism revenue to an area acts as a driver for the development of infrastructure. As tourist demands growth in a destination, more infrastructures are needed to support the needs of both the tourism industry and the local community (Walker & Moscardo 2014, Moscardo et al. 2017).

The environmental sustainability focuses on the overall viability and health of ecological systems. Natural resource degradation, pollution, and loss of biodiversity are detrimental because they increase vulnerability, undermine system health, and reduce resilience (Bellan & Bellan-Santini 2001, Shaalan 2005, Paoli et al. 2013, Mendoza-Gonzalez et al. 2018).

Many coastal areas are experiencing particular pressure from growing numbers of tourists. The coastal zone is the transition zone between the terrestrial and aquatic environment of an ocean, a gulf, a sea or a large lake and includes all the intermediate habitats (Fig. 1.5 and Fig. 1.6). The growing presence of tourist activities, the concentration of pollutants, the modification of the profile of the coast due to urbanisation interventions, can alter the balance of the biotic and abiotic components. Coastal areas are often the first environments to experience the detrimental impacts of tourism. Planning and management controls can reduce the impact on coastal environments and ensure that investment in tourism products supports sustainable coastal tourism (Tonin 2018).

Fig. 1.5 Vlora bay (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Fig. 1.6 Beach at Vlora bay (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

2

**Needs and opportunities
in Vlora**

On-the-water stakeholders in Vlora

To achieve the success and sustainability of tourism in a community, it is important to make sure that the community is represented and involved, to ensure a sense of ownership and responsibility. Knowing the opinion and perspective of local stakeholders could highlight better the needs and the opportunities. Moreover, understanding community attitudes towards sustainable development allow recommendations for ecotourism to be more realistic and achievable.

Sustainable tourism is a continuous process that requires the informed participation of all relevant stakeholders. The tourism enterprises (e.g. tour boat agencies, dive centres and marinas), while seeking long-term profitability, should be concerned about their corporate image, the relationship with their staff, and their impact on the environment.

A qualitative method was used to collect information from stakeholders using semi-structured, face-to-face interviews with the assistance of an interpreter. The local authorities and tour operators were interviewed in January 2020. Before starting the interviews, it was explained the purpose of the study. The interviews were guided by a semi-structured questionnaire. Each interview lasted between 45 minutes and an hour. The purpose of this interview was to determine the stakeholders' opinions regarding their perceptions towards the opportunities, needs and the main critical issues for sustainable tourism development at Vlora.

To integrate the information obtained during the interviews, the 29th of January, it has been organised a workshop entitled the " Sustainable tourism of water activities in Vlora bay ". It focused on the key issues of on-water sustainable tourism, the status of marine tourism in Vlora region and tourism possible impacts in Vlora region. The workshop had 28 participants (Annex 1).

Tour boat

There are sixteen tour boats that operate in Vlora. Three of them started their business between 2013 and 2017 (Fig. 2.1), while five began their activity in 2018 and seven in 2019 (Fig. 2.2, Master Harbor et al. 2019). There is a clear increase in tour boats in the last two years. The number of passengers range from 20 to 200, according to the capacity of the boat. The majority of the boats depart from Vlora Port. The boat trips are daily leaving around 9 am and return around 6 pm. The tour boats have similar routes, including these destinations: Sazani Island and surrounding areas, 2 hrs stop, Haxhi Alia cave, 45 min stop, and Shen Jani/Dhimkushta/Shen Vasil/Zhapovel, 4-5 hrs stop (Master Harbor et al. 2019).

Fig. 2.1 Tour boats at Porti i Peshkimit (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

In 2019, tour boats anchored mainly in two areas: the bay of Zhapovel and the Cape of San Vasili, in the Karaburuni Peninsula. Nine boats usually anchor at Capo di San Vasil, while two in Zhapovel bay (Master Harbor et al. 2019).

The number of local and foreign tourists who participated in a tour boat increased in 2019 compared to 2018 at K-S MPA. Part of this increment is probably due to the increased number of the boats. The peak season is from July to August (Fig. 2.2, Master Harbor et al. 2019). Given the high growth number of tour boat operators, it would be necessary to establish as soon as possible the criteria for issuing the license to these activities.

Fig. 2.2 The number of local tourists, the blue line, and of foreign tourists, the red line, who participated at a tour boat in 2018 and 2019. The green bars represent the number of tour boats (modified from Master Harbor et al. 2019).

Haxhi Ali cave is the most famous cave on the Karaburun Peninsula and a must-see for the boat trip. Although direct entry inside is only allowed for small boats, all boats make a stop to visit it. Caves are fragile habitats, which need conservation measures to preserve them (Bussotti et al. 2006, Di Franco et al. 2010, Guarnieri et al. 2012, Dimarchopoulou et al. 2018, Montefalcone et al. 2018). The need of management and regulatory plan to regulate entry into the cave with both boats and swimming is important. Some suggestions made are the creation of a timetable for boats to avoid the congestion of tourists at the same moment, the construction of a floating pier to prevent the direct entry of boats, and increased entry-ticket to the cave.

The marine and beach litters are another environmental concern. During the boat trips to reach the MPA, it is easy to find floating plastic waste. Furthermore, often the tour operators organize themselves to clean the beaches from beach litter before and during the tourist peak season. A control and sanction system for those who abandon waste on the beaches or at sea should be implemented.

Reading several tourist reviews on the Internet, the main sources of improvement suggested to some operators are adopting clear reimbursement policies in case of no exit, keeping a volume of music that is in tune with the natural environment and improving the professionalism of some employees.

Travel tickets are sold mainly through direct sales. Operators do not have a shop or a physical information point where they can be found, but are organised in outdoor stalls along the avenue leading to the port. Tickets are sold on the evening of the day before or the same morning. Only a few boats are organised to book the tour online. At the port, there is no clear signage that allows tourists to identify their boat quickly and avoid crowding. This can be improved by the use of boat signs or gates. Shady areas would be recommended. In case of delays, for example, these areas could offer refreshment to tourists who need it. A simplification of the departure procedure by the Master Harbour is also recommended.

From the infrastructure point of view, the main problem regards the port of Vlora has a difficult and sometimes impossible docking in case of strong winds.

During the journey to the protected marine area, charismatic species such as dolphins and turtles can often be observed. It would be useful to have a marine biologist or junior marine park expert on board who can explain the importance of the park, habitats and species present to interested tourists.

The cost of the tour ticket is the same for all operators (about 2'000 LEK in 2019), and the tour itinerary does not change day by day. It would be useful to diversify the offer so that could suggest more activities and alternatives for a higher number of days.

Dive centres

The popularity of recreational scuba diving has increased in recent decades, and scuba diving and the business activity related have become important tourism sectors. Scuba diving tourism is an economically important industry shown by the number of locations promoting their marine resources in efforts to become scuba diving destinations. Tourist demand for scuba diving has resulted in the rise of a niche sector, which represents high-yield tourism (Hawkins et al. 2005, Uyarra et al. 2009, Wongthong & Harvey 2014, Dimmock & Musa 2015, Lucrezi & Saayman 2017).

A range of research has examined the profile and motivations of divers, diver satisfaction and diver experiences (Palau-Saumell et al. 2014, Schoeman et al. 2016, Palau-Saumell et al. 2019), and the environmental impacts of diving on marine ecosystems (Hawkins et al. 2005, Hasler & Ott 2008, Toyoshima & Nadaoka 2015, Hammerton 2018). Scuba diving requires effective tourism management to protect ecological and cultural values, integrating social and ecological system, to achieve sustainable outcomes (Plummer & Fennell 2009, Ong & Musa 2012).

Dimmock & Musa 2015 proposed a conceptual model of the scuba diving tourism system (SDTS) where the views and concerns of multiple stakeholders together integrated to social and ecological issues in scuba diving tourism. The central elements of the underwater tourism system are the marine environment, the divers, the underwater tourism industry and the host community (Fig. 2.3).

Fig. 2.3 The key element of the scuba diving tourism system and their interaction (modified by: Dimmock & Musa 2015)

The marine environment is the crucial element on which all stakeholders in the system depend. The main stakeholders were divers (demand) and providers of underwater tourism services (scuba operators, charter operations, diving education and training, as well as associated services and tourism industries such as accommodation, transportation, catering, retail and other catering services for divers). The host community provides social and cultural resources and governments, policy makers and resource managers who manage and provide access to valuable marine environments. Understanding the problems that arise from the desire of divers to maximize their experiences, the efforts of the sector to allow these experiences while achieving commercial objectives, the needs and priorities of the host community and the duty to preserve uncontaminated environments, are the keys to ensuring a sustainable future of underwater tourism (Dimmock & Musa 2015).

There are two structured diving centres and several diving guides who operate on their own. The main underwater attractions are wrecks, coralligenous outcrops and submerged caves.

There are more than 4 main wrecks in Vlora bay, including the famous “Po Shipwreck”, an Italian hospital ship from WWII (18 m longship, 36m underwater) that sunk here in 1941 (Fig. 2.4 and Fig. 2.5). Other famous shipwrecks are Piroscrafo Luciano Wreck, Andromeda Wreck and Intrepido Wreck.

Fig. 2.4 Outer hull of the wreck “Po” (photo credit: Mauro Pazzi)

Fig. 2.5 The external bulkhead of the wreck “Po” with encrusting marine organisms (photo credit: Mauro Pazzi)

Karaburun-Sazan covers a marine area of 1.9 km and extends along the coast of the Karaburun Peninsula and the island of Sazan. In the Karaburun-Sazan MPA, it is possible to find the ruins of ancient Greek, Roman, and World War II ships, as well as coralligenous outcrops (Kashta et al. 2010, Shkurti 2019).

The most concern problem that emerged is the lack of a law on scuba and free diving and a regulatory body for this activity. The scuba diving operators apply the safety standards adopted by the respective diving schools (e.g. PADI, NAUSI, SSI, IANDT etc.), but national coordination would be important. In Albania, the scuba diving sector is in full development and in the future, it would be one of the main activities in the area. The Albanian Federation of Underwater Activities (Federata Shqiptare and Zhytjes) is also present on the territory, which has 40 associations and 70 individual people as members.

The natural environment and the artificial wrecks offer important possibilities for the development of the tourism sector linked to scuba diving. Disciplining this activity is the basis of its sustainable development from an economic, social and environmental point of view.

Local NGOs

Local NGOs interviewed were SEEP, CRCDD, Auleda, Pine Flag, Oriku Soap, INCA, ACAP, PPNEA). Local NGOs are active on both the land and the sea, depending on the skills and interests of the participants.

They mainly deal with environmental education activities in schools to raise awareness of the local community, and with the protection and conservation of the environment.

Some of these associations also deal with environmental monitoring, for example, one of these has monitored the illegal fishing activity inside Durres providing useful data to the local authorities. The involvement of citizens in supervising illegal fishing has a twofold positive return: on the one hand, if not punished, the person who committed the crime is reported, on the other, there is an awareness of the company and responsibility of citizens in the protection of their territory and environmental resources.

From an environmental point of view, a problem that is very felt by NGOs and all stakeholders concerns the treatment of wastewater. The water treatment has a limited capacity and are unable to meet the needs of Vlora, especially during the tourist season. In fact, in some areas of Vlora bay high values of *Escherichia coli* (Fig. 2.6 a) and Faecal coliforms (Fig. 2.6 b) have been detected, especially in 2012; although the values decline in last years (Fig. 2.6, source: Ministry of Environment NEA).

Fig. 2.6 Mean content of a) *Escherichia coli* 95% and b) Faecal coliforms 90% per years in Vlora bay \pm standard error

Other aspects highlighted by local NGOs are:

- the need to integrate activities between the marine and terrestrial parks
- involve as many actors as possible, including young people and the local community
- greater coordination between all NGOs activities
- diversify the tourist offer, including the tourist boat routes
- make daily packages for tourist
- strengthen public transport
- create a transport network between the city and peripheral areas
- make the information point in Vlora more visible and at more flexible times
- need to apply European standards for nature conservation

Some of these NGOs are also very active in the battle against fishing and the illegal sale of date mussel, *Lithophaga lithophaga*. Through information campaigns (Fig. 2.7), they have shown how this type of fishing has damaged coastal marine habitats. Date mussels are fished using hammers, compressors, or dynamite.

Fig. 2.7 Sample of *Lithophaga lithophaga* for environmental education aims (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Orikum Marina

Orikum Marina is the only operational marina in Albania, located 1.5 km north of the small town of Orikum in the bay of Vlora. The marina offers around 70 berths for yachts up to 15 metres in depths of up to 2.5 metres. Shelter in the marina is excellent from all wind directions.

The main problem encountered about yachting is the lack of legislation that regulates recreational tourism. For example, in the evening, it is mandatory to return to the Marina, and it is not lawful to moor in the bay. There is neither a boat shop nor a shipyard. Legislative uncertainty and the lack of infrastructure could discourage tourist boating. It would be of interest to monitor how many sailors return to Albania to get real data on the situation.

In 2019 the IX edition of the Brindisi - Vlora regatta was held. This is an important event that strengthens international relations and attracts tourists. It could be interesting and promising to set up a sailing school for the youngest to bring them closer to this discipline in contact with nature from a young age.

Professional and artisanal fishermen at Orikum and Vlora

The artisanal fishermen organised themselves into a cooperative of eight fishers. Participants agree to use sustainable fishing techniques and to sell fish for the same price in a local fish market (Fig. 2.8). Fishers worry about the environmental problem. According to their opinions and sells, cod, sea bream, monkfish, shrimp, mullet, squid, sea bream and sardines, red mullet, cod and shrimp are among the fish and shellfish preferred by tourists (Fig. 2.9).

Fig. 2.8 Local fish market (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Fig. 2.9 Fishes sell at the local fish market (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

The main problems concern illegal fishing and the lack of a shipyard. Illegal fishing is carried out using dynamite or, in the case of date mussels, with the compressor. Mediterranean lobsters, spiny lobsters and European lobsters are also caught at night, with light and scuba tanks both in the protected area and along the coast. There is no data on the quantity of fish caught illegally, on how many practices this type of fishing and how many penalties are applied each year.

Boat repair is a problem, there is no shipyard, and there is no nautical shop. In the port, there are few docks, and the boats are moored next to each other, causing inconvenience in case of departure (Fig. 2.10). There is no water and electricity, and the last dredging works to enter the port were carried out 7-8 years ago.

Fig. 2.10 Porti i Peshkimit (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Recreational fishing activities

Recreational fishing is increasing as well as freediving. Recreational fishers do not need any license and fish with hooks or trawl. The quantity of fish seems to be considerable. However, there is no official data on this. Fishermen in the area outline that local fishery resources are progressively diminishing and that their revenues have been decreasing over the years. This comment, although not supported by data, suggests that local fish resources could be overfished. Not only professional and small-scale fisheries practised in the area, but also recreational fishing (Fig. 2.11). For example, the decline of the Dusky grouper, *Epinephelus marginatus*, could be a consequence of being an intense target of spearfishing; or the intense and illegal fishing of the endolithic boring mollusc or date mussel, *Lithophaga lithophaga*, which dramatically impact the coastal habitats (Guidetti et al. 2004, Katsanevakis et al. 2011) or the intensive fishing of crustaceans (e.g., spiny lobster, *Palinurus elephas*, and European lobster, *Homarus gammarus*) which could impact the local living resources; and the trawling where is formally prohibited (Bakiu et al. 2018).

Fig. 2.11 Recreational fishing at sunset in Vlorë bay (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Acquaculture/ Mariculture in Vlorë

The entrepreneur of Mariculture- AlbAdriatico Vlorë is also the director of the national association of mariculture, which includes 12 companies, 8 from Vlorë, 4 from outside Vlorë. The aim of the association is to have a single voice if they make political requests, standardize market procedures (same price), join European standards, organize events such as fish festival, sponsorship of the region's festivities and the environment.

The company has a functional and clean structure, about 20/30 employees, of whom about ten are on call. The staff is trained (Fig. 2.12), and there are foreign experts, including a foreign veterinarian. They have

collaborations with European markets, especially Italian and German, and various certifications including European ones, which allow them to export abroad:

- GLOBALG.A.P. (Good Agricultural Practices) certification
- IFS (International Featured Standards) certification on antibiotic-free pasture
- Benthos certificate (in progress)

Through aquaculture software, like Fish Market, it can monitor in real-time the biomass of the fish present in the tanks and catch it when it reaches the size defined for sale.

Fig. 2.12 Employees at AlbAdriatico (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

The company has a type B permit, to produce 1000 tons per year, but the aim is to get type A permit to produce 2000 tons. During the peak season with the request of tourists, he must suspend the export because he does not have enough fish. It exports about 300 tons of sea bream and sea bass abroad and 700 tons on the national market.

A problem is the mariculture companies that do not comply with European standards such as the adoption of certified pasture or water monitoring.

Regional Administration of Protected Areas (RAPA) at Vlora

RAPA is responsible for the management of regional Protected Areas both marine than terrestrial, including the K-S MPA. The RAPA, together with the Coast Guard, ensures regular control for compliance with the rules within the MPA (e.g. trawling ban inside the MPA border). RAPA, besides the management of the MPA,

is also involved in the water physical-chemical monitoring of the MPA, in the monitoring of the monk seal through camera trap, and in environmental education activities.

The Visitor Centre in Radhima was established in 2017 (Fig. 2.13). It is the specific structures, designed to provide information and services about K-S MPA and it is located between the municipalities of Vlore and Orikum. The centre is visible both from the road and from the sea.

It is an important information point for the tourist about the activities promoted by the MPA, and about the Vlora region. The Visitor Centre is an added value for the tourist because is open all the year and it is easily accessible. Inside it, as well as multifunctional rooms, educational facilities, permanent and temporary exhibitions, you can find maps, guides, illustrative material and gadgets. The centre inside provides information materials and brochures not only concerning the tourist activities in the area, but also educational material on underwater marine flora and fauna and the importance of the MPA and its regulations.

At the welcome desk of the centre there are three junior experts, who are university students, two from the department of biology and one from the department of tourism. They work for the UNDP at the centre explaining the activities, doing environmental education with schools students, and sometimes go on boats to do briefings about the role of the MPA and the landscape of the peninsula of the Karaburun. Their dissemination and educational activity (e.g. Smile Albania), including the on board briefing are very important because increase the awareness of tourist and local people on environmental aspect and the important of preserve the natural landscape.

Fig. 2.12 Radhima Visitor Centre (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Marine citizen science activities are still poorly developed in the area. It has been acknowledged that divers share pictures about marine life, while fishers report when they catch unusual species. The RAPA can act as a fulcrum and a reference point for structured marine citizen science initiatives (e.g. FishMPA, Reef Check Mediterranean Sea). RAPA could organise a training event on marine citizen science that could engage dive center operator, tour boat operator, schools and university. This could be a starting point to increase awareness about these kinds of initiatives and put the basis for tourists in environmental initiatives. Moreover, some of these initiatives are focused on the benthic species and could obtain useful data for monitoring and scientific studies. In 2018 and 2019 there was a mortality event of the seashell *Pinna nobilis* along the coast of the Mediterranean Sea. Knowing the abundance and distribution of the biggest mollusc of the Mediterranean along the coast of Albania could give important information about its health status.

There is also a Sea Turtle Recovery Centre in the vicinity of Visitor Centre. The Sea Turtle Rehabilitation Facility was established in the frame of the second phase of the Marine and Coastal Protected Areas project that UNDP is implementing in Albania in cooperation with the National Agency of Protected Areas, and the financial support of the Agency of the Italian Cooperation. The structure consists of a tank and a room with basic instrumentation for treatments. In case of recovery of a sea turtle, it is transported to the centre, and a veterinarian is called. The rehabilitation of sea turtles takes place with the close assistance of the MPA administration and the fishermen's association. It is an important initiative for the protection of a charismatic species that arouses a lot of interest among tourists. Ad hoc events could be organised during the release at sea after the recovery of the turtle. Advertising these events would be an example of the positive effects of the initiatives undertaken by RAPA, and the link between the local community, among which the fishermen who saved the turtle in the sea and RAPA. This kind of initiative could trigger a virtuous circle of greater interest and involvement of the local community towards environmental issues and environmental protection.

There is no regulation for controlled entry of boats into caves. Caves are among the most fragile ecosystem that needs to be preserved. Having indicators could make policy maker and people understand the value of preserving such a fragile ecosystem. It has been noted that bats and sea swallows are no longer present in the caves most frequented by tourists. Formal regulation governing cave entry is highly recommended.

Vlora Port Authority

Every time a tour boat departs from Vlora port (Fig. 2.13), it must provide the coast guard and immigration the list of passengers. Immigration can come on board to check if the number of passengers declared corresponds to the passengers on board. The boats can depart from the authorised ports, but there is a derogation for the port of Radhima. To depart from the Radhima port, it is necessary to communicate the serial number of the boat, the type of boat, the time of departure and return, and the route.

Inspections are carried out annually on the on-board safety equipment, anti-pollution devices, and on-board equipment. If everything is in order, a certificate of conformity is issued. Then an inspector gets on board and explains the whole procedure for departing the port. Safety must come first. No fatal accident happened in 2019 on the sea. During the year, fines were made mainly for those who did not respect the minimum distance from the coast.

Fig. 2.13 Vlora port (photo credit: David Stanley)

Local authorities

Local authorities interviewed were Prefect of Vlora, Vlora Chamber of Commerce and Industry, Department of Tourism at Vlora Municipality. From the interviews with local authorities several interesting aspects emerged such as that the tourist season peak lasts just 40 days: from mid-July to mid-August. To prepare the tourist operators for the season, meetings are organised during the low season focused on education, training and receiving feedback from stakeholders to improve the coordination and the services to the tourist.

Vlora, in recent years, has attracted youth tourism for its liveliness and organised events (concerts, traditional festivals). Safety comes first and foremost. Investments have been made on beach safety. There is a lifeguard for each beach (Fig. 2.14); if not, the beach concession is not given. Also, all boats operating in the tourism sector follow the laws; this is a sign of quality. Government policies aim at the safety of tourists and increase seasonality.

Fig. 2.14 Rescue tower at Vlora bay (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

Safety at sea has been implemented and is being implemented: buoys (Fig. 2.15), signalling, corridors for entering/exiting boats from the beach. The orientation towards the municipalities is to give maximum security and greater controls.

Fig. 2.15 Buoys delimiting the K-S MPA (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

There is the will to invest in maritime tourism in a sustainable way to preserve the environment.

The main challenges raised were:

- the change in the mentality of how tourism operates, from spontaneous chaotic development to having clear rules to follow and improve;
- the making young people understand that growth and business opportunities also exist in Albania and should not necessarily be sought abroad;
- the on-the-water activities should be more diversified
- the activities must have a physical place to carry out their work;
- the need to acquire more management experience related to maritime activities

The problem of waste disposal also emerged from the local authorities that highlighted the need to educate the actors first. Furthermore, the separate waste collection is missing, apart from the waste oil collection project promoted by UNDP.

The uncontaminated nature ranges from the sea to the mountains, to the lagoon; and, with a suitable vision, the opportunities that nature offers in terms of ecotourism are many, for example from sailing to hiking, to horse riding.

Vlora Public University, Tourism Department

At the University “Ismail Qemali” there are four Faculty: economics, human science, public health and technical science. The student enrolled at the Faculty of Economics for the bachelor degree were 1’209 in the 2018-2019 academic year (Fig. 2.16, source: Administrative data from Ministry of Education Sport and Youth).

Fig. 2.16 Student enrolled at the Vlora Public University according to Faculty and educational program in the year 2018-2019 (source: Administrative data from Ministry of Education Sport and Youth)

From the marketing and tourism sector point of view, an important initiative was promoted: Smile Albania. This initiative was aimed to improve the reception of tourists by tour operators.

It has been noted that there are no inclusive tourist packages and that the activities are too concentrated on beach tourism. Acting in harmony with local authorities should diversify the tourist offer. For example, it would be necessary to improve the reception facilities for families such as children's playgrounds, but also to offer them ad hoc tourist packages. Analysing the various market niches, the solutions could be different.

Greater coordination between hotels and those offering activities on the sea would be needed. For example, the software had been proposed to hoteliers to sort their customers on different trips and activities proposed, so as to be able to obtain the minimum number to activate the activity and possibly to make customers spend less. There would have been a small percentage of economic return to hoteliers. The idea, although well structured, was not accepted and adopted.

Training for operators at the visitor centre is suggested so as to be able to offer packages cut specifically for the customer and to be able to provide targeted information according to the customer.

They are planning a star rating system that it is not yet available. This system will improve the transparency of the tourist service offered.

They highlighted the need for state intervention is necessary for the problem of insufficient water treatment plants. Like other stakeholders, they also noted the problem of waste in cities ending up at sea due to runoff (Fig. 2.17).

Fig. 2.17 Waste run off (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

3

General market analyses

Tourism trend in Albania

Tourism is one of the largest industries in the worldwide economy, and it is taking great development, especially in Albania in the last years. In 2019 the number of foreign citizens who visited Albania for holidays purpose was 6'094'889, almost double than in 2014 (Fig. 3.1).

Fig. 3.1 Arrivals of foreigners in Albania by the purpose of travel for holiday from 2014 to 2019 (source: INSTAT Albania)

The majority of foreign citizens on holiday in Albania come from European regions in particular from Southern Europe with values between 72 and 81% (Fig. 3.2). The most visits are concentrated in the two months of July and August, which define the peak season. However, there is an increase in tourists in June and September in 2019 compared to 2017 and 2018 (Fig. 3.3).

Arrivals of foreign citizens according to region

Fig. 3.2 Arrivals of foreigners in Albania by the purpose of travel for holiday divided by regions from 2014 to 2019 (source: INSTAT Albania)

Arrivals of foreign citizens in Albania for holidays

Fig. 3.3 Arrivals of foreigners in Albania by the purpose of travel for holiday by month from 2017 to 2019 (source: INSTAT Albania)

Marine tourism in Vlora demand and offer

“Marine tourism includes those recreational activities that involve travel away from one’s place of residence and which have as their host or focus the marine environment” (Orams 1999). According to this definition marine tourism embraces recreational activities both hosted by the sea (e.g. scuba diving, surfing, fishing, sailing etc.) and focus on the sea (e.g. shore-based fishing, watching a professional sailing boat competition).

The marine tourism industry can be:

- small, one-person operations: charter fishing boat operators, sea-kayak tour guides, scuba-diving instructors;
- moderate-sized private companies like dolphins-watch cruise operators, charter-yacht companies;
- business and agencies indirectly associated with marine tourism (boat maintenance shops, coastal resorts, scuba diving shops, fishing equipment suppliers, souvenir collectors);
- government and NGO agencies (monitoring and management of marine tourism).

Stakeholders offers

To delineate the supply and demand of on-the-water ecotourism at Vlora, I will report some of the results obtained from the study of Gorica et al. 2016.

According to Gorica et al. 2016, the 32% of the touristic operators consider nature-based activities very important for several reasons, such as economic and tourist satisfaction, attracting international tourists, competitive advantage, sustainable tourism development, and educative and intercultural exchange. The mainly nature-based activities offered were: recreational fishing activities, boating, parachuting, hiking, and diving.

In 2016 for the stakeholders, the most desirable nature-based activities that need to be developed in the area and offered were: diving, snorkelling, guided wildlife tours and cave exploration, because of the varied natural beauty the Karaburun area get. Other activities were also identified, such as parachute jumping, free fall, rafting and canoe tours. In 2019, most of these “alternative” activities have been offered to the tourist, but a lot less comparing to the tour boat.

In 2016, the touristic operator perceived the protection of the environment as an important aspect and some of them contribute to environmental protection through site watching and providing information to the local authorities about problems. The main environmental measure they perform was to keep the area around the structure clean.

In 2016, tourist operators had a general knowledge about the resources in the area, but there is a lack of knowledge about specific natural and cultural monuments. Five interviewees mentioned Karaburun-Sazan MPA as an essential resource; eighteen cases mentioned the sea and the marine tourism connected to it as a resource, while in 11 cases, mountain tourism is mentioned.

The most mentioned attractions were:

- Haxhi Ali Cave
- Marmiroi church
- Pashaliman
- Beaches of Karaburun
- Archaeological Park of Orik
- Museums
- Laguna
- Flora and Fauna

According to the 2016 study (Gorica et al. 2016), the most visited destinations in 2019 were: Haxhi Ali Cave, Sazan Island and Grama Bay (Fig. 3.4, source Master Harbor et al. 2019)

Fig. 3.4 Number visitors at a) Sazan Island, Haxhi b) Ali Cave and c) Grama Bay in 2019 (data source: Master Harbor et al. 2019; photo credit: a and b Eva Turicchia, c Wikimedia commons)

Furthermore, the physical and geographical conditions of the District of Vlorë and their features have an important role in the tourist offer of this geo-area (Shkurti 2013).

Tourist demand

Among tourist there is a growing interest towards nature-based activities, in particular related to the sea. Indeed, there is an increase demand for recreational fishing, boating, scuba diving, sailing and jet sky. Vlora and K-S MPA offer the perfect environment for nature-based activities able to satisfy both locals and visitors. Developing these kinds of activities could be an alternative to the beach tourism.

The “Assessment of nature-based tourism business, and tourist demand in Vlora Bay and Karaburun-Sazan National Marine Park, Albania” reported the results of 601 interviews to tourist in the area in 2016, 451 of which with local Albanian tourists (51%), while 150 were with foreign tourists (49%). International tourists came from Italy, England, Germany, Kosovo, Macedonia, USA, Greece, Poland and Ukraine. These results show that Albania is known at international tourism level, but that there is an important growth margin, especially in marketing, in order to attract as many foreign tourists as possible to the area.

72% of the tourists interviewed had a job so they could be a potential economic resource for the area. Another interesting result regards the length of stay in the bay of Vlora, where 98.3% said they stayed for a few days. Albania is a rather new tourism destination. Thanks to its impressive natural environment and a variety of attractions, Albania offers opportunities for very different types of tourism ranging from land-based activities like cultural and natural tours, hiking, biking, to water-based activities like tour boat, canoeing, sailing and diving. The temperate climate and the different natural and pristine landscapes offer a vast array of opportunity to develop nature-based tourism along all the year.

However, the touristic offers need to be diversified to manage seasonality challenges and attract tourists at different times of the year as well as to keep tourists longer in the destinations. Packages and itineraries should be tailored to offer different days of experiences and opportunities. The length of stay could thus increase from the current 4-7 nights for the 51% of the respondent to one week and longer (Fig. 3.5).

Fig. 3.5 Length of tourist stay in Vlora bay in 2016 (Modified by Gorica et al. 2016)

The foreign visitors who return the area "once or more than ones time" were 89%. This is positive result because it shows that visitors are returning to this place to spend their holidays.

The primary source of tourists' information about Vlora Bay was the recommendation by friends (41.3%). The second source of information was from the Internet, accounting for 16.8% of respondents. Other popular sources of information were tourist guides, which represents 13%, and brochures, posters and advertising, which amounted to 7.8%.

The recommendations from travel agencies had 3.2% of responses, which means the urgency to develop a marketing strategy.

The main activities planned by tourists during their stay in the bay of Vlora were swimming (29.4%), a boat trip (16.5%) and diving (15.5%). However, low percentages have been found for activities such as sport fishing, free diving, hiking, snorkelling, thus denoting a potential lack of alternative offers that need to be developed at an adequate level to be accessible and known to tourists.

72% of tourist knew that Karaburun-Sazan is an MPA. The primary sources of information for foreign tourist were tourist guides (39%) and the internet (19%), while for Albanian tourists were "the radio, TV, videos, movies" (25%) and "recommendations from friends" (23.5%).

The nature-based activities chosen by tourists at Karaburun-Sazan Marine Protected Areas were exploring caves, travelling by boat, diving, and swimming. Albanians tourists preferred most exploring caves, while foreign tourists diving (Fig. 3.6).

Nature based activities in K-S MPA

Fig. 3.6 Nature based activities preferences by tourists at K-S MNP in 2016 (modified by Gorica et al. 2016)

Finally, another aspect considered in the study concerned the nature-based activities to be improved in the bay of Vlora, according to Albanian and foreign tourists. The requests were mainly for diving and exploration of the caves (Fig. 3.7).

Fig. 3.7 Nature based activities tourists improvement preferences at Vlora Bay in 2016 (modified by Gorica et al. 2016)

This study provided an important starting point for understanding what the demand from tourists in 2016 for nature-based activities in the Vlora area. It would be desirable to propose another questionnaire to tourists for the coming year in order to check whether there have been improvements and what gaps are to be filled in order to offer an excellent tourist service.

Fishery

Small-scale fisheries (Fig.3.8) are defined as traditional fisheries involving fishing households, making short fishing trips close to shore, and selling fish mainly at local markets (Colloca et al. 2004, Lloret & Font 2013, Lloret et al. 2018).

Fig. 3.8 Artisanal fishery at Karaburun-Sazan MPA (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

In 2003, the Fishery Department of the Albanian Ministry of Environment recorded 462 small-scale fisheries vessels and approximately 900 fishermen (Cobani 2005). The availability of small-scale fisheries data is crucial for planning proper management strategies (Guidetti et al. 2010, Di Franco et al. 2016). In 2018, the Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development recorded 198 vessels in the port of Vlora, which represent 31% of the total vessels (Fig. 3.9, source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development).

Fig. 3.9 Distribution of vessels by Port (source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)

From 2014 to 2018, in Albania the gill nets are the most used, followed by trammel nets (Fig.3.10, source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development). According to the study of Bakiu et al. 2018, held in Vlora region, most of the small scale fisheries vessel that they consider in their study used trammel nets with a mesh of 34 mm on average and the most frequently used trammel being approximately 1'000 m long. Fishing trips last on average 12.4 hours, from a minimum of 5 to a maximum of 15 hours.

Fig. 3.10 Distribution of vessels by vessel type (source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)

Fishermen's perception is of a decrease in annual catches and indicates the size of the fish. Below are the data in tonnes per year from 2014 to 2018 of the catches of European anchovy, European pilchard, European hake, Gilthead seabream, Groupers nei, Monkfishes nei, Atlantic bluefin tuna and Swordfish (Fig. 3.11 a, b, c, d, e, f, g and h, respectively; source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development). The graphs refer to the whole of Albania and not only to the Vlora region (All the graphs regarding the fish catches by species are available at Annex II). It would be interesting to be able to accurately analyse catch data in this area in order to determine whether or not there is over-exploitation of the fish stock. Exploitation is, as the word suggests, an unsustainable practice from both an environmental and an economic point of view. The exploitation of the fish stock could also be aggravated by the demand during the high season by tourists. However, if overexploitation was present (technical studies on this topic are recommended), one of the main causes could be illegal fishing which is reported in various testimonies of the premises, but of which there are no data.

Fig. 3.11 Tons of catch per year of **a)** European anchovy, **b)** European pilchard, **c)** European hake, **d)** Gilthead seabream, **e)** Groupers nei, **f)** Monkfishes nei, **g)** Atlantic bluefin tuna and **h)** Swordfish (source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development)

Marine litter

A problem that was pointed out by all the stakeholders during the interviewees concerns the waste disposal and the marine litter. About 60% of the Albanian population is living in the coastal areas, while there is an increase of 15.7% on 10yrs average annual growth of tourism in Albania (UNWTO). Tourism development and the increasing number of inhabitants in the main Albanian cities like Tirana, Durrës and Vlora can increase of urban pollution in the coastal area. Not always the tourist construction along the coastal zone have been accompanied by necessary infrastructures like water supply and sewerage, collection, transport and sanitary disposal of solid wastes. Such a situation has increased the amount of solid waste, especially marine litter (Kolitari et al. 2016).

Marine litter is any anthropogenic persistent, solid material discarded, disposed of or abandoned in the marine and coastal environment. In the last decade, the huge presence of anthropogenic marine litter has started to show the impacts on marine ecosystems suffer the marine pollution. The dynamic of the phenomenon tends to an irreversible trend of environmental imbalance, for this reason, it is today a global priority for the sustainability of the planet (Galgani 2015). Marine litter negatively impacts coastal and marine ecosystems and the services they provide (Oosterhuis et al. 2014, Gall & Thompson 2015). It has environmental, economic, social, political and cultural implications as well. Marine litter could have a tremendous economic effect on economic sector such as tourism and recreation, fisheries and navigation (Brouwer et al. 2015, Rochman et al. 2016, Watkins et al. 2016, Vlachogianni 2017).

Humans produce considerable quantities of waste, and global quantities are continually increasing. The production, management and disposal of any type of waste vary in each country. Plastic is the main material of the wastes that make up marine pollution, it is omnipresent, and it represents 95% of the wastes that accumulate on the coasts, on the surfaces of the seas and on the seabed all over the world (Thiel et al. 2013, Topcu et al. 2013). The cause of this abundance is mainly due to its popularity as a consumer product, its high duration and persistence within the marine environment (Andrady 2011, Jambeck et al. 2015). The accumulation and distribution rates of the beached materials vary widely on a geographical scale. The accumulation of this waste can be influenced by several factors: size and number of coastal cities, the effectiveness of management and disposal plans, the management of coasts, maritime activities and the trend of sea currents (Galgani et al. 2000).

The terrestrial sources mainly linked to the recreational use of the coasts, cities, industries, ports and landfills, but also the discharges of wastewater, accidental losses and extreme climatic events. Some waste reaches the sea and beaches through the course of rivers (Rech et al. 2014), and other urban or industrial products may end up into the sea due to the winds. Marine sources are commercial fishing, the passage of ferries and tourist or pleasure boats, military and research fleets, offshore structures such as structures, drilling rigs and aquaculture sites (Galgani 2015).

To deal with the problems of pollution and the anthropogenic pressures exerted on marine resources, the European Commission has developed the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD, 2008/56 / EC) with the aim of protecting and promoting for minimize negative impacts on the marine ecosystem. The MFSD

represents the environmental pillar of the integrated maritime policy of the European Union. It establishes the guiding framework within which Member States must take preventive measures by 2020, and develop monitoring plans for the achievement and / or maintenance of the Good Environmental Status defined as Good Environmental Status, through the use of 11 good environmental status descriptors used to evaluate the quality of marine environments (Annex I, MSFD, 2008/56 / EC). The marine strategy is therefore based on an initial assessment, on the identification of environmental targets, and on the development of management plans, taking into account the consequences that they will have on the economic and social level.

The good environmental status descriptor used to evaluate the impacts and effects of marine and coastal pollution is descriptor 10. It requires that: "the properties and quantity of marine litter do not cause damage to the coastal and marine environment" (Galgani et al. 2013). Decision 2010/447 / EU of the European Commission highlights the criteria for evaluating the characteristics of descriptor 10. Regarding beached waste, the following is assessed:

- the trend of the quantities of waste thrown into the ground and / or deposited on the coasts, including its composition, spatial distribution and, where possible, the source;
- the trend of quantities, distribution and, where possible, the composition of microplastics.

In response to the environmental threat and the negative consequences caused by marine pollution, different types of monitoring plans have been developed to protect the coasts and to collect data related to the beach waste. Monitoring surveys are designed to facilitate the collection of information related to marine litter through voluntary individual or group cleaning. These cleaning activities and replicas carried out over time will favour the aesthetic maintenance of the beaches, and allow a better assessment of the quality of the marine environment (Ribic et al. 2012). Environmental organisations and schools intensify the involvement of volunteers through event days and / or educational activities. The behaviour of the individuals participating in the activities and of the groups is crucial in all phases of the monitoring chain and is probably influenced by knowledge, by the level of concern about this environmental problem, together with the motivation to commit to finding solutions. Therefore, understanding social habits is a fundamental step in an attempt to involve society in moving towards more sustainable purchasing, use and disposal behaviours (Hartley et al. 2015, Hartley et al. 2018). Once the monitoring has been carried out, the information obtained must be used to develop practical solutions at local, regional and potentially global level (Browne et al. 2015, Munari et al. 2016). However, these activities require considerable time and resources to collect data on a large temporal and spatial scale. The voluntary involvement of citizen citizens from broad social spectra must be instrumental for the generation of large data sets with long-term efficacy. Without the social potential of voluntary activists, the processing of data and the collection of them could be impractical due to logistical or financial constraints (Hidalgo-Ruz & Thiel 2013, Duckett & Repaci 2015). Beached waste monitoring projects vary for different characteristics of practical method and analysis techniques, and involve a constantly growing number of participants. Taxpayer states adhering to environmental sustainability policies stipulated by world environmental commissions are strengthening cooperation and

encouraging progress towards the reduction and prevention of marine solid waste, as well as increasing understanding of how it is easier and more convenient to recycle them (Nelms et al. 2017).

The monitoring plans are necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of the measures implemented to prevent or reduce the accumulation of marine pollution in a specific geographical area. Among the different monitoring plans involving citizens for the collection of data on the beach litter there are for example: OSPAR, Marine Litter Watch, UNEP / IOC and Ocean Conservancy.

The marine and beach litter is a problem that is becoming to be more serious not only in Vlora municipalities but also at the K-S MPA, as was pointed out by several stakeholders. The sources of wasting are mainly the wastewater and plastic items abounded in the beached or founded floating on the sea. A study was performed in order to investigate the marine and litter issue across the Adriatic regions. Three Albania beaches were investigated by Vlachogianni et al. 2018. The abundance of beach litter was 0.24 items/m² on averages. The contribution of items from shoreline, tourism and recreational activities sources was 47.4% (Fig. 3.12). The plastics accounted for 54.3% and the shipping activities seemed to be responsible for the higher amount of litter, 4.72% (Vlachogianni et al. 2018).

Fig. 3.12 Sources of marine litter on the basis of aggregated results at the national level (modified from Vlachogianni et al. 2018) and a plastic bottle floating at K-S MPA (photo credit: Eva Turicchia)

SWOT analysis in Vlora

A SWOT (Strengths, Weakness, Opportunities, Threats) analysis should give a succinct picture of the destination's assets and shortcomings and reveal the opportunities and challenges it faces. SWOT analysis is a commonly used tool for analysing external and internal environments simultaneously in order to acquire a systematic approach and support for a decision situation. It is indeed an important decision-making support tool, and is commonly used to systematically analyse the strategic situations and identify the level of organizations from their internal and external environments. Moreover, SWOT analysis allows for predicting future opportunities and threats, as well as quantifying effects of alternative management strategies.

Starting from the opinions of the various stakeholders related to sustainable marine tourism in Vlora, the strengths and weaknesses, as well as the opportunities and threats were summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. SWOT analyses

<p>Strengths</p>	<p>Geographic position Beautiful landscape and wildlife Pristine environment Different habitats Charismatic animals Hospitality / Friendly people Passion Active participation from the community on local issues High degree of adaptation with other cultures Dynamic city Combination of natural, cultural and tourism values Safety on the beaches (turrets and lifeguards) Environmental education at schools Infrastructure like the Radhima Visitor Centre and the Sea Turtle Recovery Centre Citizen science initiatives Virtuous examples of sustainable fishing and mariculture Language skills</p>
<p>Weakness</p>	<p>Short tourist season Little diversification of the on-water tourist offer The daily base bureaucracy for tour operators should be simplified Legislation and controls on waste to be implemented Marine litter Need to diversify the itineraries of tour boats Need for regulation for entry into sea caves Information point for tourists with limited opening hours Need to implement the infrastructures concerning the on the water tourism Illegal fishing / overfishing Lack of data on illegal fishing and sport fishing Need for greater controls and sanctions for the sale of protected species (e.g. <i>Lithophaga lithophaga</i>) Need for an ad hoc law for diving and recreational boating Lack of a shipyard and a nautical shop Lack of a hyperbaric chamber Fish farms that do not adopt European quality standards</p>
<p>Opportunities</p>	<p>Monitoring environmental programs Extension of the tourist season, interlinked all-year tourism Integration of environmental protection and tourism promotion Tourism's contribution to natural and cultural heritage Promotion of natural and cultural heritage Training course during the winter for tour operators Rating system for business Projects and initiatives to start up business Marine citizen science projects Diversification of business as economic opportunity International collaboration for tourism activities and initiatives Development of international and local marketing strategy for business Conservation situation is better than before, so it is easier to attract tourist Support from authorities Income from tourists</p>
<p>Threats</p>	<p>Risk of mass tourism No coordination in the tourism sector development Lack of tourism infrastructure Irresponsible and non professional behaviour from tour operators Uncontrolled urban and tourist development Poor public awareness and level of education on marine and coastal issues Overfishing / Illegal fishing / Dynamite Pursuit of short-term profit Disturbance and / or loss of marine habitats Increased use of natural resources Water pollution / marine litter / waste water</p>

4

Feasibility concept of
ecotourism at
Karaburun-Sazan MPA

Precondition to ecotourism development

Clarified the various interests of the stakeholders, the question of ecotourism feasibility at the K-S MPA would need to be looked at in the context of the preconditions listed below. From an investment point of view, it is considered that reasonable conditions for undertaking a tourism venture would include (Bauld 2007):

- a stable economic environment that allows the investment to operate and grow, and an effective political structure that gives security to investment;
- a level of ownership rights that allows for effective and inclusive decision-making and participation within the local community;
- perceived and actual safety and security for visitors;
- market feasibility outlining demand and return for a particular investment;
- low health risks, access to appropriate medical services, and a clean water supply;
- the ease of physical access and ability to connect to the site;
- secure land tenure and protection, with rights and powers to the relevant governing authorities;
- landscapes and/or biodiversity that provides a 'pull' factor for a range of tourist groups;
- ecosystems that have the capacity to absorb an acceptable level of tourist volumes and a variety of appropriate activities;
- a local community that has undergone awareness raising on the positive and negative impacts of tourism, as well as the potential opportunities and risks involved, and is interested in receiving tourists.

While not completely void of problems, the general environment in Albania lends itself to a favourable investment environment.

Potential environmental impacts to the Karaburun-Sazan MPA

In 2010 the area of Karaburun and Sazan were designated as an MPA, called National Marine Park of Karaburun–Sazan (K-S MPA). The Karaburun-Sazan MPA is divided into four zones with different levels of legal protection and management measures (Fig 4.1 and Fig. 4.2): (1) the core zone (CZ); (2) the effective management zone (EMZ); (3) the sustainable development zone (SDZ); and (4) the recreation zone (RZ). The CZ is a fully protected zone (no-take and no entry except for scientific research and surveillance). Within the EMZ, several activities are permitted but strictly regulated such as scientific research and monitoring, waste removal, diving, boating excursions, sailing and mooring, kayaking, water sports, visits, and wildlife watching. In the RZ and SDZ, sailing, swimming, snorkelling, anchoring, mooring, kayaking, water sports, and visiting are allowed. Small- scale fishery activities (mainly trammel nets and longlines) are allowed and regulated and authorised by the Regional Administration for Protected Areas. Within the SDZ, only non-motor water sports are permitted (Bakiu et al. 2018). The stretch of coast that includes the K-S MPA is the site of a number of human settlements and activities, such as cities, ports, fish farms, tourism operations, and a number of large-scale fisheries and small-scale fisheries (Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.2). Mapping was done using the free and open-source geographic information system QGIS ver. 3.4 (qgis.org).

Fig. 4.1 Main commercial activities in Vlorë province (source: UNDP)

Fig. 4.2 Main commercial activities in Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay (source: UNDP)

Diagnostic cartography consists in the cartographic representation of a set of synthetic indicators for the evaluation of the territory to be managed. In 1992, Agenda 21 enunciated the need for diagnostic tools for the coastal zone, which including the sustainable development of coastal and marine areas (Bianchi et al. 2012).

To produce the cumulative impact map, the marine territory was divided into territorial units (TU), a 1 km grid. Each cell was scored according to the sum of the presence of human activity that can cause an environmental impact in that cell. The final territorial scores of the cells are then reported in classes obtained by dividing them into quintiles. A colour was assigned to each class using red, orange, yellow, light green and dark green, in order, to indicate a decreasing cumulative impact. The impacts that were considered to produce the cumulative impact map were: tourist boat routes, diving and anchoring points, the presence of restaurants or camping sites, fish farm areas and water pollution derived from the punctual values of faecal coliforms and *Escherichia coli* of the year 2018 (Fig. 4.3 and Fig. 4.4). Spatial analysis and mapping were done using the free and open-source geographic information system QGIS ver. 3.4 (qgis.org).

Sazan Island has very low to low cumulative impacts values, indicating that anthropogenic pressures in the area are low or absent. The Karaburun Peninsula is in good condition, but with cumulative impact values ranging from high to very high in some areas, generally near restaurants, diving spots, along tour boat routes and close to fish farms. Vlora bay has on average low and moderate cumulative impacts (Fig. 4.3 and Fig. 4.4).

More data on possible impacts distributed equally along the coast would allow more accurate maps.

Fig. 4.3 Cumulative impact map in Vlorë province (source: UNDP)

Fig. 4.4 Cumulative impact map in Vlorë province, close up of Vlorë bay (source: UNDP)

On the water sustainable tourism stakeholder perception

The data were collected via a structured questionnaire survey administered to the main stakeholders (the English version of the questionnaire is available at Annex III). The questionnaire contained three main sections. The first captured socio- demographic data such as age, level of education and covered business details. The second section, using semantic scales, measured resident's perceptions concerning tourism and dealt with details on social and economic business profile. The last invited the operators to indicate their level of agreement, using semantic scales (ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree), with statements concerning the on-the-water sustainable tourism in their area.

Fourteen operators in the tourism sector replied to the questionnaire, including 8 in the tour boat sector, 2 in diving, 3 in artisanal and recreational fishing, and 1 tourist guide. Although the number of responses is limited, it is quite representative of the local reality.

Towards a better understanding of the social profile of the respondents and their relationship with the local authorities and local community, a series of questions was proposed.

14% of interviewers agree that local authorities support sustainable tourism. However, 72% said that this only happens sometimes (Question 3a, Fig. 4.5). Positive is the fact that 57% believe that the local community often supports sustainable tourism, a front of 7% who instead say that this happens rarely (Question 3b, Fig. 4.5). Local authorities often promote sustainable tourism for 21% of respondents, while the community often promotes it for only 7% of respondents (Question 3c and 3d, Fig. 4.5). The state of the marine environment is often taken into account by both local authorities and the local community, for 50% and 43% of respondents, respectively (Question 3e and 3f, Fig. 4.5).

Fig. 4.5 Respondent opinion about their relationship with the local authorities and local community on the on water sustainable tourism theme

According to the respondent, the on-water tourism business creates leisure opportunities for people, “probably yes” for 21% and “definitely yes” for 29% (Question 3g, Fig. 4.6).

Fig. 4.6 Respondent opinion about the leisure opportunities create by on-water tourism business

There is a positive general agreement about that on-water tourism represents the heartbeat of this area, 50% of the respondents “strongly agree” on that (Question 3h, Fig. 4.7). Vlora is considered a world-class destination

for all the respondents (strongly agree 64%, agree 36%; question 3i, Fig. 4.7). All the respondents agree that the growth of the on-water sustainable tourism is important (strongly agree 57%, agree 47%; question 3l, Fig. 4.7).

Fig. 4.7 Respondent opinion about the on-water tourism and the area

The natural environment is very important for 93% of the interviewed (Question 3m, Fig. 4.8).

Fig. 4.8 Respondent opinion on the importance of natural environment

The reasons for choosing a site, for example, for a boat excursion or a dive, can be different, but the main aspect must be safety. All respondents considered the marine weather conditions for choosing the site to be very important (86%) to important (14%; question 5b1, Fig. 4.9). Other very important aspects are the daily organisation (71%; question 5b2, Fig. 4.9) and the landscapes (71%; question 5b4, Fig. 4.9). Customer requests are moderately important for 8% and very important for 64% of respondents (Question 5b5, Fig. 4.9). The number of customers is important for the choice of the site for 57% of respondents (Question 5b3, Fig. 4.9).

Fig. 4.9 Respondent motivation behind the choice of a site

A briefing concerning the safety procedures during sea activities is always made by 43% of the respondent, while sometimes by 50% and never by 7% (Question 5c, Fig. 4.10).

Fig. 4.10 Respondent habit of making a safety briefing

Not all companies have a refund policy for customers if the scheduled activity cannot be performed (Fig. 4.11 a). 86% of the respondents have never organised a public event (Fig. 4.11 b).

Fig. 4.11 a) refundable policy, b) public events

43% of the respondents don't have an Internet website to advertise their business (Fig. 4.12 a), while 79% use social media as the main tool for marketing (Fig. 4.12 b). 93% of the respondents collaborate with other local business in the area (Fig. 4.12 c).

Fig. 4.12 marketing aspects a) website, b) social media and c) collaboration with other business

When asked if the on-water sustainable tourism creates employment, respondents strongly agreed (43%) and agreed (50%; question 7a, Fig. 4.13). The respondents strongly agree (29%) and agree (57%) that on-water sustainable tourism creates more opportunities for local businesses (Question 7b, Fig. 4.13). The on-water sustainable tourism ensures maintenance of infrastructure and services in the area for 79% of the respondent (agree 50% and strongly agree 29%; question 7c, Fig. 4.13). The 14% disagree that on-water sustainable tourism

competes with cultural traditions of the area (Question 7d, Fig. 4.13), while the 21% disagree that on-water sustainable tourism increases the total cost of living in the area (Question 7e, Fig. 4.13). 71% of the respondents agree that on-water sustainable tourism increases property and accommodation value in the area (Question 7f, Fig. 4.13). There is indecision for 36% of the respondents if on-water sustainable tourism generates revenue for conservation and environmental management (Question 7g, Fig. 4.13).

Fig. 4.13 Respondent economic perception about the on-the-water sustainable tourism

64% of respondents believe that the protected marine area benefits from sustainable tourism (Fig. 4.14 a). There is no fee to enter the protected marine area (93% do not pay any fees and 7% have not replied; Fig. 4.14 b). For 86% of those interviewed, the MPA promotes local business (Fig. 4.14 c).

Fig. 4.14 Respondent MPA perception on a) benefits, b) fees and c) local business

According to 72% of the respondent, the MPA firmly enforces on-water safety rules (Fig. 4.15 a). 72% as well agree that the MPA firmly enforces proper tour boat/diving/snorkelling etiquette, while 7% disagree (Fig. 4.15 b). The MPA works to improve the quality of the on-water tourism business for 64% of the interviewed (Fig. 4.15 c).

Fig. 4.15 Respondent MPA perception on a) enforcement on safety rules, b) etiquette and c) quality of tourism business

The communication between the on-water tourist business and MPA management is perceived as effective by the 57% of the respondent (Fig. 4.16 b). In comparison, the requests and concerns of the on-water tourist business are seen as addressed by the MPA for 43% of the interviewed (Fig. 4.16 a). The customers explicitly request to visit the MPA in 57% of the cases against 29% (Fig. 4.16 c).

Fig. 4.16 Respondent MPA perception on a) requests and concern, b) communication and c) customers request

When asked about the impact of the establishment of the MPA on the creation of jobs, implementation of new or improved services, Improved infrastructures, the increase income, respondents felt that the establishment was positive (Fig. 4.17). On the other hand, when measuring the impact of the establishment of the MPA on the increase of traffic, the congestion of beach facilities, the increase of noise, they felt that it had a negative effect (Fig. 4.17).

Fig. 4.17 Respondent perception on the establishment of the MPA (P = positive, N= negative, NA= not available)

36% of the respondent admitted that the tourists are not actively engaged in litter picking (Fig. 4.18 a). 43% of the respondent thinks that tourism has caused a reduction in wildlife abundance and diversity (Fig. 4.18 b).

Fig. 4.18 Respondent perception on a) tourist engaged in litter picking and b) reduction in wildlife abundance

50% of the interviewed always do a briefing on the cultural heritage of the area, while 34% just sometimes (Fig. 4.19 a). On the other hand, 29% of them always do an environmental briefing, while 57% sometimes (Fig. 4.19 b).

Fig. 4.19 Briefing policy on a) cultural heritage and b) environment

The favourite customers' fauna is dolphins, turtles, monk seals and fishes (Fig. 4.20 a), while the favourite habitats are caves, coralligenous formations and wrecks (Fig. 4.20 b).

Fig. 4.20 Customer preference on a) flora and fauna and b) habitats

50% of respondents agree, and 21% disagree that new buildings, from tourism, have changed the appearance of our town for the better (Question 10a, Fig. 4.21). The 71% agree that the money spent on advertising to attract more tourism to town is a good investment (Question 10b, Fig. 4.21). 30% disagree that tourism has harmful effects on the natural environment (Question 10c, Fig. 4.21). 43% of them agree both that touristic sites (e.g. caves, beaches, dive spots) in the area are overcrowded during the peak seasons (Question 10d, Fig. 4.21), and that on-water sustainable tourism is good for the local economy (Question 10e, Fig. 4.21). 64% are undecided if the tourists care about the marine environments in this area (Question 10f, Fig. 4.21). Finally, 50%

of respondents agree, and 21% strongly agree that improving the sustainability of on-water tourism can attract more tourist (Question 10g, Fig. 4.21).

Fig. 4.21 Respondent tourism perception

There is no clear direction among the respondent if the on-water tourist businesses are actively involved in marine research: 33% has answered "never", while 22% "rarely", 22% "sometimes" and 22% "often" (Question 11a, Fig. 4.22). There is no clear direction too about if the requests and concerns on marine environmental issues of the on-water tourist business are addressed by scientists (Question 11b, Fig. 4.22). The communication between the on-water tourist business and scientists is effective for 55% of the respondent (44% often, 11% always; question 11c, Fig. 4.22). Scientists promote marine environmental education in the area "often" for 78% of the respondent and "always" for 22% (Question 11d, Fig. 4.22).

Fig. 4.22 Respondent science perception

5

Conclusions

Karaburun-Sazan MPA has the potential to develop on water sustainable tourism towards the development and application of best practices. Ecotourism is considered an opportunity as it is in line with the conservation principles and the sustainable development goals set in by the United Nations in 2015.

The evaluation of the area has revealed six important elements in the development of the sustainable on-the-water activities in the Vlora region:

1. The K-S MPA have sea and landscape appeal, characterised by almost pristine habitat. Natural attractions include, but are not limited to, the caves, cliffs, bays, beaches, crystal water, but also the diversity of the marine benthic flora and fauna. There are important and protected marine habitats such as coralligenous habitats or seagrass meadows. Moreover, the convention of Barcelona has classified the K-S MPA as a Specially Protected Areas of Mediterranean Importance;
2. Accessibility to the location is good and convenient, especially for visitors which aim to gain experience and learn about the natural resources and cultural landscapes that they visit. Vlora is located in the southwest of Albania. Geographically, the city is situated in the Bay of Vlora and the foothills of the Ceraunian Mountains at the Strait of Otranto along the Adriatic and the Ionian Sea. The A2 motorway is a four-lane motorway stretching between Fier and Vlora along the Adriatic seacoast of Albania. The Vlora Bypass is 29 kilometres long linking A2 with coastal SH8 along the Albanian Riviera. Vlora International Airport is an airport project expected to finish by 2023, in the city of Vlora. This will be the third international airport in Albania after Tirana International Airport and Kukës International Airport. In addition to the construction of the airport, the project includes a marina and farmhouse site. Ferries connections are well established between Albanian ports and the major ports across and along the Adriatic Sea. From Vlora bay, it is possible to reach the Karaburun peninsula, on average, in about an hour, an hour and a half;
3. On-the-water tourism activities are poorly differentiated and without a definite long period business plan. There is a willingness on the part of entrepreneurs to adopt sustainable tourism practices, but at the moment, there is no clear vision of this and a multi-year plan in which stakeholders can meet and join. The administration should favour with suitable tools those who undertake investments towards sustainability;
4. Vlora local community welcome the development of tourism in the area. However, because of the social, economic and especially understanding of sustainable tourism that is still lacking, the development of sustainable tourism practices still has many challenges. The benefits of sustainable tourism activities and the importance of the K-S MPA have been felt by both the public and local governments;
5. The market potential is promising, especially for the increasing number of tourists arriving in Albania and for the world's population trends in their use of leisure time. The forces that drive

the changes that occur at the global level and regulations at the local level have an impact on lifestyles and selecting tourist destination regions. An increasing number of foreign tourists appreciate the adoption of sustainable practices and the care and protection towards the environment.

6. Management and services in relation to tourism could be improved. An entrance ticket to the K-S MPA would be desirable, the income of which would be managed directly by RAPA. An economic income of this type would allow the park to have the financial means to carry out more controls and monitors in the area, maintenance and improvement works of the park, as well as training for its employees and volunteers. Moreover, citizen science events could be coordinated by RAPA. These would lead not only to collect data of scientific interest and required by European regulations (e.g. Marine Strategy Framework Directive) but also to increase the cohesion of the social fabric, get to know the MPA better, and possibly involve tourists.

Citizen science conservation action

Reef Check Italia is no-profit scientific association intent to the protection and recovery of Mediterranean reefs (www.reefcheckmed.org). Founded in 2008, Reef Check Italia aims to stimulate local actions to protect areas that are still little damaged and to recover those damaged through the adoption of a shared and standardised protocol (i.e. Underwater Coastal Environment Monitoring Protocol, U-CEM protocol) across the Mediterranean countries. The U-CEM protocol is intended to assess the ecological status of the Mediterranean marine coastal habitats. Scuba divers and snorkelers can apply it after a short training.

Together with a scientific monitoring protocol for monitoring the Karaburun-Sazan MPA, it could be useful to apply also a standardised monitoring protocol that involves the citizens and visitors (i.e. U-CEM protocol). MPA managers should indeed include dive centres, tour agencies and university in contributing to the monitoring and preservation of the habitats supporting their own business activities. Moreover, the involvement of citizens in environmental monitoring may increase their understanding and awareness concerning the marine environment, which is essential for the conservation of the habitats.

The University of Vlora represents another important opportunity for sustainable tourism development. Marine biology students could do internships either at the dive centres or at the tourist agencies that make snorkelling trips, and at the Visitor Centre of Karaburun-Sazan MPA. In this way a double advantage would be obtained: the internship students would have experience in the field, while the structures/business would have a marine biologist who, besides helping them in the various daily activities, would provide an essential contribution in the field of environmental education of tourists and in protecting the marine environment.

6

Annexes

Annex I List of participants at the workshop

IMPROVING COVERAGE AND MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS OF MARINE AND COASTAL PROTECTED AREAS - 2

Desk meeting

“Turizmi i qendrushem i aktiviteteve te ujit ne gjirin e Vlores”

Vendi: Salla e Konferencave, Hotel Pavaresia
E merkure, 29 Janar, 2020, Vlore

Nr.	Emer Mbiemer	Institucioni/Organizata
1.	ENDERIT GJUMAJ	PESTRKAPNI
2.	ADRIATIK SELAMI	OAZI BLU DIVING CENTER
3.	Eaton Mislaku	OAZI BLU Diving center
4.	Valentina Heliq	Aujia Tejeta
5.	Luriana Dacci	COGIA R40
6.	Endro Galonshaj	INCA
7.	Luisi GJAVI	MARINA ORIKON
8.	Nexhip Hysolaj	AKZM Vlore
9.	Luan Hysaj	AKZM-Vlore
10.	LORENÇESKINJA	KAP. PORTI T VLORE
11.	Skënder Durmishaj	organizatë për mbrojtje
12.	Enna Melicli	Asnjë shtetë Uingue
13.	Admin Malaj	PORTI DETAR VLORE
14.	Adrian Beqiri	ISHMELUT
15.	LIRA SPIRO	Prerfekt Vlores
16.	Bisiana Deliaj	Prerfekte Vlores
17.	Adriana Bekaj	UNDP - Albania
18.	Kameta Sushkaj	UNDP - Albania
19.	Dejvis Gjafa	UNDP - Albania
20.	Oliver Galonshaj	AKZM Vlore
21.	Donisa Peshaj	AKZB Vlore
22.	SONIA SINA	AKZB Vlore
23.	Eno Dodibiba	UNDP
24.	Violeta Zura	UNDP
25.	Miranda Hoxha	GREEN VLORE
26.	Thomas Keki	CERCI 1998
27.	Dionid Petaj	UNDP
28.	Eva Totocchia	UNDP consulting
29.		
30.		

(Photo credit: Eno Dodibiba)

Annex II Fish catches by species in Albania from 2014 to 2018

The species are displayed in alphabetical order, and the unit of measure is tons per year.

Source: Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development

European conger

European flounder

European hake

European pilchard

Annex III On the water sustainable tourism questionnaire

On-water sustainable tourism questionnaire

According to the World Trade Organisation, the sustainable tourism is: “**Tourism that takes full account of its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, addressing the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities**”.

This survey aim is to investigate your opinion about sustainable tourism related to your business.

The results of this survey will be presented in aggregate form, and personal information will be not disclosed.

When it is not specify, please write an “X” to indicate your choice.

Section1: Profile of the interviewees and basic information about their business activity													
1. Personal information													
Name and Surname: _____													
Nationality: _____				Gender: _____				Male / Female					
Age: _____				Education: _____									
2. Business information													
Company name: _____				Email: _____									
2a. Please specify which kind of business you are involved to (More than one answer is allowed)													
Tour boat		Touristic agencies		Recreational fishing activities									
Dive centres		Marina		Other (please, specify) ...									
2b. Status in business													
Owner		Manager		Tour guide									
Instructor		Receptionist		Other (please, specify) ...									
2c. Opening date (year) of your business? _____													
2d. How many vessels do you own? If 1 or more, please specify the boat typology and the number of people that it can carry													
	Typology of the boat						Number of people that it can carry						
1)													
2)													
3)													
4)													
2d. Number of people and type of employment of the staff													
Staff member type				N°		Season of work							
Full-time employees						Winter		Spring		Summer		Autumn	
Occasional employees						Winter		Spring		Summer		Autumn	
Volunteers						Winter		Spring		Summer		Autumn	
2e. Which are the months of peak season?													
Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec		

Section 2: Socio-economic profile

3. Social profile					
3a. The on-water sustainable tourism is supported by the local authorities	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
3b. The on-water sustainable tourism is supported by the local inhabitants	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
3c. The local authorities are involved in marketing to promote on-water sustainable tourism	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
3d. The local inhabitants are involved in marketing to promote on-water sustainable tourism	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
3e. The local authorities care about the state of marine environments in the area	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
3f. The local inhabitants care about the state of marine environments in the area	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
3g. On-water tourism business creates leisure opportunities for people	Definitely	Probably	Possible	Probably Not	Definitely Not
3h. On-water tourism forms part of the “heartbeat” of this area	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
3i. This area is a world class destination for on-water sustainable tourism	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
3l. The growth of the on-water sustainable tourism is important	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
3m. Is it important the natural environment for you?	Very Important	Important	Moderately Important	Slightly Important	Unimportant
4. Economic profile					
4a. According to your business, in 2019 which was the average number of:					
	Daily tour		Customers per daily tour		
Winter					
Spring					
Summer					
Autumn					
4b. Which is the cost of different typologies of daily tour?					
Daily boat tour within the Marine Protected Area (MPA)			Daily boat tour outside the MPA		
Daily dive tour (2 dives)			Recreational fishing daily tour		
Other (please, specify)					
4c. What types of activities do you offer to your customers during the peak season besides daily tour?					
Answer:					

5. Tourism profile					
5a. Please add the information required about the sites frequently visited by tourists.					
	Name of the site	Kind of activity (diving, snorkelling, fishing, other)	Habitat type (e.g. cave, beach, wreck)	Mooring typology (buoy or anchor)	
1					
2					
3					
4					
5					
6					
7					
8					
9					
5b. What is the motivation behind the choice of one site?					
Weather condition	Very Important	Important	Moderately Important	Slightly Important	Unimportant
Daily organisation	Very Important	Important	Moderately Important	Slightly Important	Unimportant
Number of customers	Very Important	Important	Moderately Important	Slightly Important	Unimportant
Seascape/Landscape	Very Important	Important	Moderately Important	Slightly Important	Unimportant
Customer's request	Very Important	Important	Moderately Important	Slightly Important	Unimportant
5c. Do you do a briefing concerning the safety procedures during sea activities to your customers?					
Yes, always	Yes, sometimes		No	Not applicable to my business	
5d. Do you have a clear refundable policy?					
	Yes	No	I don't know	Not applicable to my business	
5e. Have you ever organise public events such as sporting competition or citizen science initiatives?					
Yes	No	I don't know		Not applicable to my business	
If yes, please specify which kind and which was on average the tourist and local people turnout					
Answer:					
6. Marketing					
6a. Do you have an internet website to promote your business?			Yes	No	Not Applicable to my business
6b. Do you use social media to promote your business?			Yes	No	Not Applicable to my business
6c. Do you collaborate with other local business?			Yes	No	Not Applicable to my business

Section 3: on-water sustainable tourism perception

7. Economic perception					
7a. The on-water sustainable tourism creates employment	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7b. The on-water sustainable tourism creates more opportunities for local businesses	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7c. The on-water sustainable tourism ensures maintenance of infrastructure and services in the area	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7d. The on-water sustainable tourism competes with cultural traditions of the area	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7e. The on-water sustainable tourism increases the total cost of living in the area	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7f. The on-water sustainable tourism increases property and accommodation value in the area	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
7g. The on-water sustainable tourism generates revenue for conservation/environmental management	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
8. Marine Protected Area (MPA) perception					
8a. The on-water sustainable tourism benefits the MPA	Yes	No	I don't know		
8b. The on-water tourism activities pay a fee to the MPA	Yes	No	I don't know		
8c. The MPA promotes the sustainable development of local businesses directly dependent on it	Yes	No	I don't know		
8d. The MPA firmly enforces on-water safety rules	Yes	No	I don't know		
8e. The MPA firmly enforces proper tour boat/diving/snorkelling etiquette	Yes	No	I don't know		
8f. The MPA works to improve the quality of the on-water tourism business	Yes	No	I don't know		
8g. Requests and concerns of the on-water tourist business are addressed by the MPA	Yes	No	I don't know		
8h. Communication between the on-water tourist business and MPA management is effective	Yes	No	I don't know		
8i. Is scuba diving activity allowed in the MPA?	Yes	No	I don't know		
8l. Is tour boat activities allowed in the MPA?	Yes	No	I don't know		
8m. Is anchorage allowed within the MPA?	Yes	No	I don't know		
8n. Do your customers explicitly request to visit the MPA?	Yes	No	I don't know		
8o. Following there is a list of potential impact related to the establishment of the MPA on the society. Please, add a "P" if you think it could be a Positive impact or an "N" if you think it could be a Negative impact. Add an "NA" (Not assessed) if you do not have an opinion.					
Creation of jobs		Increase traffic		New or improved services	
Congestion of beach facilities		Change in town character		Increase opportunities for cultural exchange	
Increase noise		Improved infrastructures		Increase income	
Increase in local taxes		Spoiling of the natural environment		Improved recreational facilities	
9. Environment awareness perception					
9a. The on-water tourism promotes environmental education in the area	Yes	No	I don't know		
9b. The on-water tourism promotes conservation actions in the area	Yes	No	I don't know		
9c. The tourists are actively engaged in litter picking	Yes	No	I don't know		

9c. The tourists are actively engaged in litter picking				Yes	No	I don't know
9d. The on-water tourism has caused reductions in wildlife abundance and diversity in this area				Yes	No	I don't know
9e. Which are the aquatic flora and fauna that customers prefer to find during the tour? (Indicate a maximum of 3 answers)						
Algae	Seagrass meadow (e.g. <i>Posidonia oceanica</i>)	Gorgonians	Red coral	Big crustaceans (e.g. lobster)		
Fishes	Turtles	Dolphins	Monk seal	Sponges		
Other (please, specify)						
9f. In your experience, which are the main habitats requested by customers to visit? (Indicate a maximum of 3 answers)						
Sandy bottoms	Seagrass meadow	Rocky bottoms	Coralligenous formations			
Caves	Wrecks	Archaeological sites	Not relevant for my business			
Others (please, specify)						
9g. Is there a specific interest among customers for issues related to environmental conservation and marine biology?						
No			Yes			
If yes, which is the main motivation in your opinion?						
Love for the sea			Innate sensitivity toward the marine environment			
Curiosity			Other (please, specify)			
9h. Do you do a briefing concerning the history and cultural heritage to your customers?						
Yes, always		Yes, sometimes		No		Not applicable to my business
9i. Do you do a briefing concerning the environment to your customers?						
Yes, always		Yes, sometimes		No		Not applicable to my business
If yes, do you sensitise the customers about the possible damage that can be caused to the marine environment?						
Yes			No			
9l. Do you carry out activities to raise environmental awareness?						
Yes			No			
If yes, please specify:						
9m. Do you do separate waste collection?						
Yes			No			
9n. Do you think that your business is sustainable from an environmental point of view?				Yes	No	I don't know
10. Tourism perception						
10a. New buildings, from tourism, have changed the appearance of our town for the better	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
10b. Money spent on advertising to attract more tourism to my town is a good investment	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
10c. Tourism has harmful effects on the natural environment	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
10d. Touristic sites (e.g. caves, beaches, dive spots) in the area are overcrowded during the peak seasons	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	
10e. On-water sustainable tourism is good for the local economy	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	

10f. On-water tourists care about the marine environments in this area	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
10g. Improving the sustainability of on-water tourism can attract more tourist	Strongly Agree	Agree	Undecided	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
10h. Specify the geographical origin of your customers in 2019:					
National (e.g. Tirana, Vlora):		International (e.g. Italy, Spain):			
11. Science perception					
11a. The on-water tourist business are actively involved in marine research	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
11b. Requests and concerns on marine environmental issues of the on-water tourist business are addressed by scientists	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
11c. Communication between the on-water tourist business and scientists is effective	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
11d. Scientists promote marine environmental education in the area	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never

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